

Hierarchical NiO/ZnS nanocomposite for optimal photocatalytic performance

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ABSTRACT

Hierarchical nickel oxide (NiO) has recently garnered significant interest due to its abundant unsaturated bonds, oxygen vacancies, and defect sites. These features act as reaction centers, promoting effective photocatalytic performance. However, the fast photogenerated charge recombination rate impedes its practical utilization. To tackle this problem, we deposited nanoscale ZnS on hierarchical NiO using the Pseudo-successive ionic layer adsorption and reaction process, which is a facile, vacuum-free, cost-effective, and suitable for deposition at room-temperature. The enhanced dye degradation performance can be ascribed to the precise deposition of ZnS and the notable surface structure, which together create a dynamic p-n heterojunction that effectively suppresses photogenerated charge carriers. Various techniques like UV-visible spectrometer, X-ray diffraction, photoluminescence spectroscopy, scanning electron microscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectrometer, electrochemical spectroscopy, and photocurrent were used to assess the electrical, photocatalytic, optical, and morphological properties of the p-n heterojunction. The reactive species involved in dye degradation were identified and investigated using scavenger studies, and a plausible reaction mechanism was proposed.

1. Introduction

Due to the increased use of dyes, especially in the textile and cosmetic industries, the demand for water purification and cleaning has risen accordingly to ensure clean and safe water for aquatic life and land organisms [1,2]. Accordingly, different strategies and nanomaterials have been developed to effectively break down dye molecules in water [3]. To efficiently degrade dye molecules, various photocatalysts, particularly oxides like NiO, are gaining attention because of their stability, photocatalytic activity, simple synthesis process, non-toxic nature, and cost-effectiveness [4–6]. The photocatalytic performance of pure NiO mainly depends on its shape, size, crystal orientation, and specific surface area [7]. Therefore, different NiO morphologies, such as nanosheets [8,9], nanofibers [10], nanowires [9], and hierarchical structures [11], have been created to improve photocatalytic efficiency. Among these, the hierarchical structure with many unsaturated bonds and defect sites is especially effective because it greatly enhances

photocatalytic activity [12,13]. However, pure hierarchical NiO cannot be used frequently because of its prompt charge recombination rate and broad bandgap [14].

To enhance the photocatalytic activity of pristine NiO, an effective strategy is to incorporate n-type semiconductors such as ZnO, TiO₂, SnO₂, and ZnS to it. For example, Begum et al. fabricated an SnO₂/NiO nanocomposite using the co-precipitation technique, signifying improved photocatalytic activity compared to pure NiO, mainly due to reduced photogenerated charge recombination [15]. Similarly, Yu et al. created a hierarchical NiO/TiO₂ p-n heterojunction through hydrothermal synthesis, showing improved dye degradation performance mainly by suppressing photogenerated charge recombination [11]. Likewise, Hashim et al. and Singh et al. developed hierarchical NiO/ZnO nanocomposites, which showed enhanced photocatalytic activity mainly due to efficient charge transport [16,17]. Additionally, Rao et al. fabricated ZnS/NiO nanocomposites via the hydrothermal technique to boost the photocatalytic efficiency of pristine NiO [18]. In these n-type

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Fig. 1. An experimental diagram illustrates the numerous steps involved in the fabrication of a nanocomposite.

materials, ZnS is often employed for forming p-n junctions because of its unique properties and its ability to be effectively deposited using the pseudo-successive ionic layer adsorption and reaction (p-SILAR) technique. This inspired us to synthesize a hierarchical NiO/ZnS heterojunction using p-SILAR technique to improve the photocatalytic activity of pristine NiO.

In this study, an effective p-n heterojunction is formed by depositing an optimal amount of nanoscale ZnS on hierarchical NiO using the cost-effective p-SILAR method. The synthesized p-n heterojunction features a hierarchical structure with many unsaturated bonds and defect sites,

providing an efficient pathway for the separation and transport of photogenerated charge carriers. These factors collectively enhanced the performance of the synthesized nanocomposite. Various techniques such as UV-visible spectrometry, photoluminescence spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, electrochemical spectroscopy, and photocurrent measurements were employed to evaluate the electrical, photocatalytic, optical, and morphological properties of the synthesized p-n heterojunction.

Fig. 2. (a) SEM picture (b), energy dispersive spectroscopy results, and (c) elemental area mapping of bare NiO.

Fig. 3. (a) SEM image (b) energy dispersive spectroscopy result and (c) elemental area mapping of NiO/ZnS nanocomposite.

2. Experimental section

2.1. NiO hierarchical nanoflowers synthesis

The hydrothermal method was used to create the hierarchical nanostructures of NiO. 3.2 mL of ethylene diamine was added dropwise to a 0.5 M solution of nickel nitrate $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ prepared in DI water while stirring constantly. After that, a 7 M NaOH solution in DI water was added to the above mixture, and the solution was then continuously agitated for 30 min. In order to create $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$, the prepared solution was then put into an autoclave the temperature was set to 150 °C for 240 min. Finally, the hierarchical NiO was obtained by annealing the synthesized samples at 400 °C for 5 h.

2.2. Preparation of p-n heterojunction

Using the procedure outlined by Khan et al. [19], the cationic and anionic precursors for p-SILAR process were prepared. Zinc nitrate $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ was utilized as the cationic precursor, whereas sodium sulfide ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was used as the anionic precursor for ZnS deposition. A zinc nitrate $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution in methanol with a concentration of 0.1 M was used as the cationic precursor. In a centrifugal tube, take 20 mL of cationic solution and 0.15 g of synthesized powder. After that, it was centrifuged for five minutes at 9000 rpm. Then, methanol was added to the tube and centrifuged at the same speed to remove any loosely attached Zn ions. Then, add an anionic solution followed by centrifugation. Finally, methanol was added to remove any loosely bound anionic ions. Different p-SILAR cycles (2, 4, 6, and 8) were applied to ensure adequate deposition of ZnS upon hierarchical NiO.

2.3. Characterization

Utilizing a Bruker-D2 powder diffractometer, the crystallinity and phase purity were assessed. Using (SEM, Hitachi SU-5000), the morphological features and elemental composition were examined. To investigate the surface chemical composition, an X-ray photoelectron spectrometer (Thermo-VG Scientific, ESCALAB 250) was utilized. Each sample's photocurrent response was measured using an electrochemical analyzer (CHI-B600). The recombination rate of photogenerated charge carriers was examined using the RAMHR, PL spectrometer (HORIBA-Lab), and the CHI 760 D, CH Instruments, to get the electrochemical impedance spectra. The absorbance behaviour was studied using

Fig. 4. (a) X-ray diffraction spectra of pristine NiO and NiO/ZnS nanocomposite.

(JASCO, V-650).

2.4. Photocatalytic activity assessment

The synthesised p-n heterojunction's photocatalytic activity was assessed by measuring the degradation of rhodamine B (RhB) dye. First, 7.2 mg of RhB dye were uniformly dispersed by sonication and stirring in 1000 mL of fresh deionized water [20,21]. Subsequently, take 200 mL of dye solution in a beaker and pour 100 mg of the synthesized samples, followed by sonication and stirring. Next, UV irradiation was used at room temperature to evaluate the photocatalytic performance of the synthesized nanocomposite. Furthermore, freshly prepared solutions were supplemented with specific scavenging agents such as isopropyl alcohol, ammonium oxalate, and p-benzoquinone to evaluate the role of holes (h^+), hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$), and superoxide radicals ($\bullet\text{O}_2^-$) in dye degradation.

3. Results and discussion

The successful formation route of both pristine and p-n heterojunctions is shown in the schematic (Fig. 1). Pristine NiO demonstrates a compact and non-symmetrical structure, as seen in Fig. 2a and Fig. S1.

Fig. 5. Core level spectra of (a) Ni 2p (b) O 1s, (c) Zn 2p, and (d) S 2p.

The EDS (Fig. 2b) results demonstrate that hierarchical NiO possesses 46.8 % Ni and 53.1 % O, matching well with the published literature [22]. The distribution of Ni and O was verified via area mapping, as seen in Fig. 2c. Additionally, Fig. 3a and Fig. S2 demonstrate the morphology of p-n heterojunction. While Fig. 3b and Fig. 3c demonstrate EDS and area mapping of the synthesized heterojunction. The elemental area mapping in Fig. 3c shows that ZnS was uniformly deposited on hierarchical NiO, providing a large number of junctions for effective transferring of photogenerated charge carriers. The ZnS deposition on hierarchical NiO was optimized using the EIS technique as revealed in Fig. S6.

To evaluate phase purity of the synthesized p-n heterojunction and pristine NiO XRD analysis were performed as revealed in Fig. 4. The crystallographic planes (311), (220), (200), and (111) are confirmed by the pure NiO sample's distinct peaks at 75° , 62.9° , 43° , and 37° , respectively [23,24]. The XRD pattern of p-n heterojunction demonstrates an extra peak at 2θ angle of 28.8° , which corresponds to ZnS (111) plane [19].

Furthermore, XPS study was done to evaluate in-depth the surface chemical composition of the synthesized nanocomposite. The survey spectrum (Fig. S3) indicates the presence of each constituent element along with core-level spectra of C 1s. The Ni 2p spectra can be divided into two prominent Ni 2p_{3/2} and Ni 2p_{1/2} peaks, located at 854.4 and 871.4 eV, respectively, along with their two satellite peaks as revealed in Fig. 5a [18]. Also, O 1s core level spectra give three prominent peaks allocated to O-C=O, C-O, and Ni-O, respectively, at their respective binding energy position as revealed in Fig. 5b [25]. Zn 2p core level spectra give two prominent peaks assigned to Zn 2p_{3/2} and Zn 2p_{1/2}, respectively, at their respective binding energy position as revealed in Fig. 5c [26,27]. Similarly, S 2p spectra can be divided into two prominent peaks, S 2p_{3/2} and S 2p_{1/2}, at their respective binding energy position as revealed in Fig. 5d [28,29].

The absorbance behaviour of both samples was assessed using UV irradiation. A slight red shift was observed in the p-n heterojunction, indicating enhanced light absorption, mainly due to interfacial charge transfer, band bending, and the formation of intermediate energy levels

Fig. 6. (a) UV absorption and (b) Tauc plot of pure NiO and NiO/ZnS p-n heterojunction.

Fig. 7. (a) EIS and (b) Photocurrent spectra of pure NiO and ZnS/NiO nanocomposite.

Fig. 8. RhB dye's trend of UV light absorption as a function of UV irradiation duration, illustrating how UV light causes photocatalytic degradation of RhB when (a) NiO and (b) NiO/ZnS are present, while (c) represents Dye degradation performance, and (d) is the reaction rate constant.

at the NiO-ZnS interface, as shown in Fig. 6a [29]. The bandgap energy values for the respective samples were 3.4 and 3.27 eV, determined from the Tauc plot in Fig. 6b.

The Mott-Schottky (M-S) analysis was conducted for both pristine NiO and ZnS, as revealed in Fig S4. The M-S plot of NiO exhibits a negative slope, confirming its p-type semiconducting behaviour due to hole-dominated charge carriers [30]. In contrast, the M-S plot of ZnS shows a positive slope, characteristic of an n-type semiconductor dominated by electrons [31]. These findings clearly demonstrate that the NiO/ZnS heterostructure forms a p-n junction, which facilitates internal electric field formation and effective charge separation across the interface.

Furthermore, a thorough assessment of the charge transfer performance was conducted using the Nyquist plots obtained from EIS analysis, as shown in Fig. 7a. The equivalent circuit (Fig. S5) includes a

charge transport resistance (R_t), a capacitor (C), and a series resistance (R_s) [32,33]. A larger semicircle diameter in the Nyquist plot indicates higher charge recombination [32]. As depicted in Fig. 7a, the semicircle diameter decreases due to ZnS deposition, which signifies efficient charge separation and migration. Additionally, Table S1 provides the values of R_s , R_t and C. Moreover, a comprehensive evaluation of the charge transfer performance was performed through photocurrent measurement, as shown in Fig. 7b [17]. The synthesized p-n hetero-junction exhibits higher photocurrent intensity, demonstrating effective suppression of charge recombination.

To assess the photocatalytic efficacy of p-n heterojunction, RhB dye degradation was performed. The intensity of the peak became lower and lower when the light striking time was increased, as revealed in Fig. 8a-b. While Fig. 8c demonstrates C/C_0 against "t" in which C_0 represents the starting concentration and (C) is the dye concentration after irradiation

Fig. 9. Schematic representation of photogenerated charge carriers, generation, separation, and migration in NiO/ZnS p-n heterojunction.

Fig. 10. Stability test of NiO/ZnS p-n heterojunction using RhB dye degradation.

time t . As revealed in (Fig. 8c), the p-n heterojunction effectively degrades the RhB dye mainly due to enhanced migration of charge carriers. A higher K_c (Fig. 8d) value was observed for p-n heterojunction photocatalyst, indicating a higher forward reaction [34]. The primary cause of the improved photocatalytic performance is the efficient junction creation between ZnS and hierarchical NiO, which effectively separates the photogenerated charge carriers. Hence, just after 120 min, 84.5 % of the RhB dye was degraded by the synthesized p-n heterojunction.

Moreover, scavenging tests were carried out to assess the functions of $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$, $\bullet\text{OH}$, and h^+ in the dye degradation as revealed in Fig. S7 [35]. Scavengers like AO and BQ significantly suppressed the dye degradation performance. While IPA addition to the solution has less effect on the performance, indicating its minor role in dye degradation.

Fig. 9 shows a schematic representation of the potential charge generation and separation in the synthesized nanocomposite. From the band gap and M-S analyses, the VB and CB values for the n- and p-type semiconductors are as follows:

- ZnS: $E_{\text{CB}} = -0.77 \text{ V}$, $E_{\text{VB}} = +2.88 \text{ V}$ (vs Ag/AgCl)
- NiO: $E_{\text{VB}} = +2.92 \text{ V}$, $E_{\text{CB}} = -0.53 \text{ V}$ (vs Ag/AgCl)

While the CB and VB values of the n-type and p-type semiconductors on the NHE scale are as follows.

- ZnS: $E_{\text{CB}} = -0.573 \text{ V}$, $E_{\text{VB}} = +3.077 \text{ V}$ (vs NHE)
- NiO: $E_{\text{VB}} = +3.117 \text{ V}$, $E_{\text{CB}} = -0.333 \text{ V}$ (vs NHE)

When p-type and n-type semiconductors are combined, a p-n

heterojunction is formed at their interface. The diffusion of electrons and holes via the interface of p-n heterojunction does not stop until it reaches the Fermi level equilibrium, creating an intrinsic electric field, also called a "charged" region [10,11]. Photogenerated electrons and holes are created when light strikes the synthesized p-n heterojunction because of the thermodynamically advantageous band gap position, the electrons swiftly move from the conduction band (CB) of NiO toward the lower CB of ZnS [36]. The excited electrons in CB of ZnS transform absorbed oxygen into active $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ radicals, which play an essential role in dye degradation. Since valence band (VB) position of NiO is higher than that of ZnS, which promotes the transfer of h^+ from ZnS to VB of NiO. The synthesized NiO/ZnS p-n heterojunction effectively degrades RhB dye mainly due to effective suppression of photogenerated charge carriers. The RhB dye molecules are effectively decomposed by the principle of oxidation/reduction processes, which are driven by $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ and h^+ species.

Additionally, stability tests (Fig. 10) were conducted to assess the synthesized photocatalyst's durability and stability [37]. The synthesized p-n heterojunction demonstrates durability and stability because after five consecutive cycles, the efficiency has decreased only by about 4 % from value 84.5 % to value 80.5 %.

4. Conclusion

In summary, a simple, vacuum-free, and cost-effective p-SILAR method was used to synthesize a hierarchical ZnS/NiO p-n heterojunction. The heterojunction photocatalyst was characterized by morphological, structural, and physicochemical techniques. Lower PL and EIS spectra of the synthesized heterojunction compared to pristine NiO resulted in enhanced optoelectronic response and significantly improved photocatalytic degradation of RhB dye. Therefore, the synthesized photocatalyst can be considered an effective and economical option for applications in contaminant treatment and environmental purification.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Khalid Alshammari: Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Ayesha Samreen:** Visualization, Investigation, Data curation. **Gohar Ali:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sameer Alghanm:** Visualization, Investigation. **Talal Hamza Maghrabi:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Junaid Khan:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Aas Ghazi:** Visualization, Investigation. **Nadeem Qureshi:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ayman Osama:** Visualization, Investigation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.dwt.2025.101529](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dwt.2025.101529).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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